

Effect of Adding Corn Cobs Fermented with *Ganoderma* spp. to the Soil on Some Growth Indicators of Cucumber Plants

Ahmad S. A. Al-Kaabi

Directorate of Agricultural Extension and Training,
Ministry of Agriculture, Najaf, Iraq

Ahmad M. Hussien

Department of Plant Protection, College of Agriculture,
University of Kufa, Iraq

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Abstract:

This study involved the isolation and identification of certain pathogenic agents causing seed rot, seedling death, and root rot in cucumber plants. The pathogens were isolated from infected cucumber plants, and their pathogenicity was tested. Their control was examined using the fleshy fungi *G. applanatum* and *G. resinaceum*. The results revealed significant differences among the fungal isolates obtained from cucumber plants, indicating a substantial effect on reducing the germination rate of cucumber seeds used in the study. The fungus *F. oxysporum* showed a significantly greater impact compared to the other fungal isolates, with a germination rate of

13.13%. The isolate *R. solani* followed, showing a germination rate of 16.13%, compared to the control treatment, which recorded a germination rate of 90%. The field experiment results demonstrated the superiority of the treatment (50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. resinaceum*) combined with the pathogenic fungi in achieving the highest total phenolic content in the leaves, reaching 138.64 ppm. In comparison, the treatment (50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. applanatum*) resulted in a total phenolic content of 137.47 ppm. Regarding the total glycoside content, the treatment (50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. resinaceum*) in combination with the pathogenic fungi recorded the highest content, reaching 57.65 ppm. In the same treatment (50% soil + 50% corn inoculated with *G. applanatum*) the glycoside content was 56.91 ppm. Regarding peroxidase enzyme activity, the treatment with pathogenic fungi (50% soil + 50% corn cob fermented with *G. resinaceum*) produced the maximum peroxidase level at 20.23 ppm, which was significantly better than other treatments the , except the treatment (50% soil +). 50% *G. applanatum*), in which 19.67 ppm of peroxidase was recorded. Regarding total sugar content, the treatment (50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. resinaceum*) combined with the pathogenic fungi recorded the highest total sugar content, reaching 7.89 ppm. This was significantly superior to the other treatments, except for the treatment (50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. applanatum*), which recorded a total sugar content of 7.57 ppm.

Keywords: *Ganoderma ressensense*, *Ganoderma applanatum*, *Fusarium oxysporum*.

Introduction

Biological control agents are considered safe and environmentally friendly methods, ranking

among the most promising and widely accepted approaches for crop management. Among successful agents in this regard are extracts from fleshy fungi, primarily from the class of

basidiomycetes, containing substances with antibacterial, antifungal, and antiviral properties (Yang et al., 2022). Ganoderma, extracts from this rule fungi, are known for the inhibition substances besides the various health benefits (Cör and Knez, 2022).

Among bioactive compounds in Ganoderma are fiber, polysaccharides, oligosaccharides, triterpenoids, peptides, proteins, alcohols, and phenols as well as minerals like zinc, copper, iodine, selenium, germanium, and iron, besides vitamins and amino acids. It also has some other compounds such as carbohydrates, glycosides, phenolic compounds, and tannins. These substances and compounds possess putative therapeutic properties for a broad spectrum of diseases, and antimicrobial effects (Liang et al., 2018; Cör and Knez, 2022).

The cultivation of Ganoderma fungus was started in 1969 in the People's Republic of China and later became widespread in Asian countries especially Japan and Korea. Initially, cultivation involved inoculating natural tree trunks, one meter in length, and burying them in the soil (Bijalwa et al., 2020). Subsequently, this fungus was cultivated on various low-cost agricultural substrates. Numerous agricultural residues, such as sawdust, tree stems, and residues from cereal crops, which are rich in cellulose and lignin, were utilized for growing *Ganoderma*. Shomali et al. (2019) reported that the fruiting body of *G. adspersum* contains high concentrations of phenolic compounds. Alves et al. (2012) identified 23 types of phenolic compounds extracted from various fleshy fungi, which demonstrated inhibitory effectiveness against several types of microorganisms. Gandermin, a protein isolated from the fruit bodies of Ganoderma, showed antifungal activity against *Botrytis cinerea*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, and *Phylospora piricola* (Wang and Ng, 2006). Hot water extract Ganoderma and polysaccharides isolated by gas chromatography techniques showed inhibitory effects against plant pathogens, such as *Erwinia carotovora*, and fungal pathogens, including *Penicillium digitatum* and *Botrytis cinerea* (Bai et al., 2008).

Materials and Methods

Isolates of *Ganoderma* spp.

The isolates *Ganoderma resinaceum* and *Ganoderma applanatum* were obtained by Dr. Mahmoud from the Plant Protection Directorate, Ministry of Agriculture. These isolates are registered in the Global Genetic Bank under the identifiers *Ganoderma applanatum* isolate Has.AA-6 and *Ganoderma resinaceum* isolate Has.AA-8, with the global accession numbers ON834523.1 and ON834527.1, respectively (Mahmoud, 2023).

Corn Cob Medium

Corn cobs were obtained from the Grain Silo of the Ministry of Trade, Babylon. Cobs were chopped into pieces of 3–4 cm and moistened (approximately 70% w/w), with excess water removed. Corn cobs prepared were transferred to transparent bags of 1 kg capacity, and filled with 1 kg of fresh-weight corn cobs in each bag. Bags were sterilized with an autoclave set at 121°C and 15 psi pressure.

After cooling, fungal inoculum of *Ganoderma* spp. was added at a rate of 5% of the substrate's weight (Jouda, 2021). The openings of the bags were tightly tied with a string, and the inoculated bags were moved to an incubation room with insulated walls (4 × 3 m, heating and cooling system) at 25 ± 2°C, where the fungi grew on the corn cobs until full colonization.

Isolation and Purification of Fungi Causing Seed Rot and Seedling Death in Cucumber

Roots and stems of infected cucumber plants were cut into small segments of about half a centimeter to 1 cm and washed thoroughly in water to clean any existing remnants and soil matter. The sections were then immersed in 1% sodium hypochlorite solution for three minutes with the intention of sterilization disinfected subsequently washed several times with sterilized distilled water to remove any traces of chemicals used. The excess moisture was removed using sterile filter paper. The sterilized plant pieces were then placed onto pre-prepared Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium in Petri dishes, with four pieces per dish and three replicates. The petri were incubated at 25 ± 2°C for 2–4 days. A 2–3 mm piece was cut out from

the tip of fungal colony with the help of sterile needle, and inoculated to the center of Petri plate supplemented with new PDA medium which were incubated at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 days to get pure cultures of the fungus (Pathak, 1973).

Isolation of Fungi from Infected Plants

The results of Table (1) show fungi isolated from the roots of infected cucumber plants, and soil (Rhizosphere) surrounding infected plants. The fungal species detected are also shown in the table, including *Alternaria*, *Aspergillus*, *Chaetomium*, *Cladosporium*, *Fusarium*, *Macrophomina*, *Penicillium*, *Rhizoctonia*, *Trichoderma*. The presence of these fungi can have a positive or negative effect on cucumber roots, rhizome soil, or plant surfaces grow in plants so these. The ability of the fungi to be pathogen on cucumber seed germination and seedling growth.

Table 1. Fungi Isolated from Cucumber Plants and the Surrounding Rhizosphere Soil

Fungi	Fungi
<i>Alternaria alternata</i> .	<i>Cladosporium Cladosporioides</i> .
<i>A. solani</i>	<i>Chaetomium lobosum</i> .
<i>A. citri</i>	<i>Cladosporium herbarium</i> .
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> .	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> .
<i>A. fumigatus</i> .	<i>F. solani</i> .
<i>A. niger</i> .	<i>Macrophomina phaseolina</i>
<i>A. ochraceous</i> .	<i>Penicillium</i> sp.
<i>A. silverra</i> .	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> .
<i>A. terreus</i> .	<i>Trichoderma barzianum</i>

Propagation of Fungal Inoculum Used in the Study

Millet seeds, obtained from agricultural offices in Al-Najaf Al-Ashraf, were sterilized as previously described and used for preparing fungal inocula. Each flask was inoculated with five discs (0.5 cm in diameter) of the selected fungal isolates grown on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium, aged 7 days. Each flask was inoculated individually with one fungal species. The flasks were incubated at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 days, with shaking every 3 days to ensure proper aeration and

uniform fungal colonization of the seeds (Dewan, 1989).

Pathogenicity Test of Fungi Isolated from Cucumber Seedlings in Petri Dishes

The study was conducted at the Postgraduate Laboratory of Plant Protection, College of Agriculture, University of Kufa. For cucumber seeds, seeds were soaked in 1% sodium hypochlorite solution for 3 min before use and then rinsed with plain distilled water and dried with sterile filter paper. Seeds were placed in Petri dishes (10 seeds per pot) on standard potato dextrose agar (PDA). A 0.5 cm diameter disc from the PDA comprising one of the isolated fungi, which was 7 days old, was placed at the center of each dish. Each fungal isolate was tested individually, with three replicates per fungus. A control treatment was included by planting cucumber seeds in the same manner but without fungal inoculation.

The dishes were incubated at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and after 10 days of seed germination, the percentage of germinated seeds and rotted seedlings was calculated using the following formulas.

$$\text{Germination Percentage} = \frac{\text{Number of germinated seeds}}{\text{Total number of seeds}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Seedling Mortality Percentage} = \frac{\text{Number of dead seedlings}}{\text{Total number of seedlings}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Field Experiment

The field experiment was carried out in one of the greenhouses of the College of Agriculture Agricultural Research Station University of Kufa at the spring agricultural season of 2024. The design of the experiment was a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) comprising three blocks with twenty-one treatments in each block. Soil was prepared by plowing, leveling, and 3 drip irrigation pipes were laid for every block at an emitter spacing of 15 cm. Soil was sterilized with 5% formaldehyde for 3 days and aeration for another 3 days. Seeds of the

cucumber cultivar “Super Fares” were seeded in polystyrene trays and transplanted into the field at 30-day-old seedlings. Each treatment contained three replicates of seedlings planted in plastic bags (5 kg) with 15 cm spacing. The treatments applied in the experiment were as follows:

1. Healthy plant (control).
2. Soil + *R. solani*.
3. Soil + *F. oxysporum*.
4. 75% soil + 25% corn cobs.
5. 50% soil + 50% corn cobs.
6. 75% soil + 25% corn cobs + *R. solani*.
7. 50% soil + 50% corn cobs + *R. solani*.
8. 75% soil + 25% corn cobs + *F. oxysporum*.
9. 50% soil + 50% corn cobs + *F. oxysporum*.
10. 75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with *G. applanatum*.
11. 75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with *G. resinaceum*.
12. 50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. applanatum*.
13. 50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. resinaceum*.
14. 75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with *G. applanatum* + *R. solani*.
15. 50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. applanatum* + *R. solani*.
16. 75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with *G. resinaceum* + *R. solani*.
17. 50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. resinaceum* + *R. solani*.
18. 75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with *G. applanatum* + *F. oxysporum*.
19. 50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. applanatum* + *F. oxysporum*.
20. 75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with *G. resinaceum* + *F. oxysporum*.

21. 50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. resinaceum* + *F. oxysporum*.

Estimation of Total Phenols in Leaves

One mL of the extract was placed in a test tube and then 1 mL of 0.05 N HCl and 1 mL of Arno reagent, 10 mL of distilled water, and 2 mL of 4% sodium hydroxide NaOH solution were added and the absorbance was measured at 515 nm and contained there.. The absorbance at 515 nm was measured. In addition, sample preparation of control (blank), not including the sample, was prepared with all reagents. A catechol calibration curve was used to quantify phenolic concentration. Catechol (0–1.2 mg/mL) was added to six test tubes to prepare the standard curve. Each tube received 1 mL of HCl, 1 mL of Arnow's reagent, 2 mL of 4% NaOH and 10 mL of distilled water. Absorbance was recorded at 515 nm and a calibration curve was plotted for catechol concentrations vs. their corresponding absorbance values (Mahadevan; Sridhar, 1986).

Estimation of Total Glycosides in Leaves

A volume of 1 mL of the extract was mixed with 10 mL of Baljet reagent and kept at room temperature for one hour. And the absorbance was at 495 nm then 20 mL of distilled water was added to the reaction mixture. The glycoside concentration was measured with a standard calibration curve prepared from Securidaside at concentrations of 0 to 1.2 mg/mL. The same procedure was followed for the above-mentioned standards, and the calibration curve was constructed to establish the relationship between concentration and absorbance at 495 nm (Tofighi et al., 2016).

Estimation of Peroxidase Enzyme Activity in Leaves

The estimation of peroxidase (POD) enzyme activity was determined using fresh vegetative samples ground in a ceramic mortar with 10 mL of phosphate buffer (KH₂PO₄) under chilled condition. The mixture was filtered through filter paper, and the filtrate was kept in refrigerator at 2°C for further enzymatic activity analysis. This procedure was based on Cooper (1977) method. One drop of enzyme was used

to measure absorbance with a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 436 nm. Absorbance readings were taken at intervals of 30 seconds until a period of 5 minutes.

Estimation of Total Sugars in Leaves

Sample was weighed 5 grams into 100 mL volumetric flask and fill to the mark with distilled water. After that, the flask was placed in water bath for 30 min. Then this solution was filtered through filter paper, and the filtrate was collected in a 250 mL volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with distilled water. 50 mL of the solution was pipetted to a 100 mL volumetric flask and subsequently, 6.5 mL of concentrated hydrochloric acid (35.4%) was measured into a measuring cylinder and added. The flask was incubated in a water bath for 20 min. 3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator were then added and saturated sodium hydroxide solution used to neutralize the mixture. The solution was subsequently loaded into a burette. 15 mL of the prepared solution was added from the burette to a conical flask, and 12.5 mL of Fehling's solution A and B was added from a measuring cylinder. The resultant mixture turned blue, and the blue color was then boiled off on the stove. The solution immediately turned blue again by adding two drops of methyl blue indicator. The prepared solution was titrated from the burette until the endpoint was reached, and the readings were documented. It was calculated as per sugar content (Singh, 2011).

Estimation of Vitamins in Plant Leaves

100 mg of leaves from the previously ground plant were weighed and dissolved in 10 mL of distilled water. Then, the mixture was put on a shaker for 30 min at temperature 60–70°C and filtered by a 0.22 µm filter, and the filtrate was injected into HPLC.

Results and Discussion

Effect of Fungi Isolated from Infected Cucumber Plants on the Germination Percentage of Cucumber Seeds

The results shows significant differences among the fungal isolates obtained from infected

cucumber plants, indicating their considerable impact on reducing the germination percentage of cucumber seeds (Table 2). *F. oxysporum* showed the most pronounced effect, with a germination percentage of 13.13%, significantly lower than the other fungal isolates, except for *R. solani*, which had a germination rate of 16.13%. In contrast, the control treatment recorded a germination rate of 90%. The germination percentages for other fungal isolates ranged between 33.67% and 80%. Most of the isolated fungi reduced cucumber seed germination to varying degrees. The ability of *F. oxysporum* to significantly reduce germination is attributed to its production of enzymes and toxins that degrade plant cell walls, destroying cellulose-based structures and playing a critical role in pathogen virulence. This fungus is known to produce toxins such as Fusaric acid, Dehydro Fusaric acid, and Lycomarsmin, which are metabolic compounds capable of inhibiting seed germination (Mezzomo *et al.*, 2019).

Table 2. Pathogenicity of Fungal Isolates Obtained from Infected Cucumber Plants Using Cucumber Seeds under Laboratory Conditions

Fungi	Germination %
Control	90
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	40
<i>A. solani</i>	73.33
<i>A. citri</i>	40
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	66.67
<i>A. niger</i>	83.33
<i>A. flavus</i>	33.67
<i>A. silveira</i>	76.67
<i>A. terreus</i>	73.33
<i>Chaetomium globosum</i>	86.67
<i>Cladosporium Cladosporioides</i>	43.33
<i>C. herbarium</i>	53.33
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	13.33
<i>Macrophomina phaseolina</i>	46.67
<i>Penicillium sp</i>	83.33
<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	16.33
<i>T. harzianum</i>	80
L.S.D	14.05

Effect of Corn Cobs Fermented with Fleshy Fungi and the Interaction between the Pathogenic Fungi *F. oxysporum* and *R. solani* on Total Phenolic Content in Leaves (ppm)

Table (3) demonstrates that corn cobs fermented with *G. applanatum* and *G. resinaceum* significantly influenced the total phenolic content in cucumber leaves. The highest phenolic content was observed in the treatment (50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. resinaceum*), with a total phenolic content of 138.64 ppm, significantly outperforming the other treatments. This was followed by the treatment (50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. applanatum*), which recorded a phenolic content

of 137.47 ppm. The lowest phenolic content was observed in the control treatment (soil only), with 132.81 ppm. For the pathogenic fungi individually, the phenolic content in leaves inoculated with *F. oxysporum* and *R. solani* was 135.47 ppm for each.

Regarding the interaction treatments, the highest phenolic content was observed in the combination of (50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. resinaceum*) and the pathogenic fungus *R. solani*, recording a phenolic content of 138.75 ppm, which was significantly superior to all other treatments. The lowest phenolic content was found in the interaction between (soil only), with a value of 131.26 ppm.

Table 3. Effect of Corn cobs Fermented with Fleshy Fungi and the Interaction between the Pathogenic Fungi *F. oxysporum* and *R. solani* on Total Phenolic Content in Leaves (ppm)

Treatment	Control	<i>R. solani</i>	<i>F. oxysporium</i>	Mean
Soil only	131.26	133.68	133.71	132.81
75% soil + 25% corn cobs	132.05	133.57	133.78	133.12
50% soil + 50% corn cobs	132.46	133.94	133.73	133.34
75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. applanatum</i>	135.55	135.12	134.99	135.26
50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. applanatum</i>	137.65	137.21	137.46	137.47
75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. resinaceum</i>	135.84	135.68	135.64	135.66
50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. resinaceum</i>	138.52	138.75	138.65	138.64
Average of pathogenic fungi	134.76	135.47	135.47	
LSD	Cobs=0.28	Fungi=0.18	Interaction=0.49	

High content of growth-inhibitory substances for many different microorganisms, including fungi, has been proven for Ganoderma fungi. They have been shown in several studies as being effective in controlling fungal plant pathogens. The results reinforce the biosynthetic pathways of Ganoderma species forming such bioactive compounds that contribute to the presence of antifungal activities as well, which is supported by the study of Naveen (2018) about Ganoderma fungi containing antifungal bioactive compounds through phenolic materials and various other components.

Phenolic compounds provide the derivative salicylic acid (SA), which plays an important role in plant resistance. SA acts as a signaling

molecule for plant cells, alerting them before or during infection. Once accumulated, it triggers a response not only at the infection site but throughout the entire plant, inducing Systemic Acquired Resistance (SAR) (Heil, 1999; Kopcewicz *et al.*, 2004). Moreover, phenolic compounds possess antioxidant properties by inhibiting the formation of free radicals, such as iron and copper ions. This ability is attributed to their functional groups, including hydroxyl and carboxyl groups. Plants with high tannin content provide additional resistance against pathogens. These ions are commonly found in aquatic plants, such as water lilies, as observed through phenolic analysis using methanol (Bozin *et al.*, 2008; Lavid *et al.*, 2001).

Effect of Corn Cobs Fermented with Fleshy Fungi and the Interaction between the Pathogenic Fungi *F. oxysporum* and *R. solani* on Total Glycoside Content in Leaves (ppm)

Table (4) demonstrates that corn cobs fermented with *G. applanatum* and *G. resinaceum* significantly influenced the total glycoside content in cucumber leaves. The highest glycoside content was observed in the treatment (50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. resinaceum*), which recorded a value of 57.65 ppm, significantly outperforming other treatments. This was followed by the treatment (50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. applanatum*), with a

glycoside content of 56.91 ppm. The lowest glycoside content was observed in the control treatment (soil only), which recorded 50.36 ppm. Regarding the pathogenic fungi, the glycoside content in leaves was 54.46 ppm for both *F. oxysporum* and *R. solani*.

In terms of interactions, the highest glycoside content was observed in the combination of (50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. resinaceum*) and the pathogenic fungus *F. oxysporum*, which recorded a value of 58.31 ppm, significantly surpassing all other treatments. The lowest glycoside content was found in the interaction between (soil only), with a recorded value of 48.87 ppm.

Table 4. Effect of Corn Cobs Fermented with Fleshy Fungi and the Interaction between the Pathogenic Fungi *F. oxysporum* and *R. solani* on Total Glycoside Content in Leaves (ppm)

Treatment	Control	<i>R. solani</i>	<i>F. oxysporum</i>	Mean
Soil only	48.87	51.27	50.97	50.36
75% soil + 25% corn cobs	49.14	51.61	51.84	50.84
50% soil + 50% corn cobs	49.19	52.32	51.98	51.16
75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. applanatum</i>	53.63	54.59	54.83	54.38
50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. applanatum</i>	55.67	57.33	57.72	56.91
75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. resinaceum</i>	53.93	54.98	54.99	54.66
50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. resinaceum</i>	56.36	58.15	58.31	57.65
Average of pathogenic fungi	52.34	54.46	54.46	
LSD	Cobs=0.58	Fungi=0.38	Interaction=1.01	

Ganoderma spp. It has numerous antimicrobial activities and different compounds including glycosides, phenolic compounds and tannins with prominent antimicrobial potency (Isaka et al., 2016).

The inhibitory effect of glycosides is due to the glycosides ability to inhibit cell membrane activities, bind membrane lipids, and inhibit membrane enzymes. Also, tannins can have an inhibitory role to the enzyme peroxidase (Gleadow and Moller, 2014). *Ganoderma* spp have been shown in several studies contain glycosidic compounds and ascorbic acid, both of which have prominent antioxidant and antimicrobial effects (Wood et al., 2021).

Fermented corn cobs with *Ganoderma* spp. played a role in increasing glycosides in cucumber plants. This may be attributed to the ability of the secondary metabolites and enzymatic

products of *Ganoderma* spp. to activate genes responsible for glycoside production, which is one of the mechanisms of systemic resistance induction in plants. This aligns with similar studies demonstrating that systemic resistance induction in various plant species is triggered by filtrates of yeasts and filamentous fungi (Ahmed et al., 2021; Hassan and Yousef, 2023).

Effect of Corn Cobs Fermented with Fleshy Fungi and the Interaction between the Pathogenic Fungi *F. oxysporum* and *R. solani* on Total Peroxidase Content in Leaves (ppm)

Table (5) shows that corn cobs fermented with *G. applanatum* and *G. resinaceum* significantly influenced the total peroxidase content in cucumber leaves. The results revealed that the highest peroxidase content was observed in the treatment (50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented

with *G. resinaceum*), with a value of 20.23 ppm, significantly outperforming other treatments. This was followed by the treatment (50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. applanatum*), which recorded a peroxidase content of 19.67 ppm. The lowest peroxidase content was observed in the control treatment (soil only), with a value of 7.98 ppm. For the pathogenic fungi, the peroxidase content in leaves was 16.38 ppm for *F. oxysporum* and 15.91 ppm for *R. solani*.

Regarding interactions, the highest peroxidase content was observed in the combination of (50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with *G. resinaceum*) and the pathogenic fungus *F. oxysporum*, with a value of 20.98 ppm, significantly surpassing all other treatments. The lowest peroxidase content was recorded in the interaction between (soil only), with a value of 2.03 ppm.

Table 5. Effect of Corn Cobs Fermented with Fleshy Fungi and the Interaction between the Pathogenic Fungi *F. oxysporum* and *R. solani* on Total Peroxidase Content in Leaves (ppm)

Treatment	Control	<i>R. solani</i>	<i>F. oxysporum</i>	Mean
Soil only	2.03	10.70	11.22	7.98
75% soil + 25% corn cobs	2.15	10.95	11.36	8.15
50% soil + 50% corn cobs	2.34	11.08	11.51	8.31
75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. applanatum</i>	16.47	18.81	19.36	18.21
50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. applanatum</i>	18.45	20.18	20.40	19.67
75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. resinaceum</i>	16.66	18.85	19.81	18.44
50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. resinaceum</i>	18.92	20.80	20.98	20.23
Average of pathogenic fungi	11.00	15.91	16.38	
LSD	Cobs=1.59	Fungi=1.04	Interaction=2.76	

The fungus *Ganoderma spp.* contributes to enhancing resistance against pathogens by working in conjunction with peroxidase enzymes produced by plant resistance genes. This process strengthens cell walls, impeding pathogen advancement and penetration. These treatments contain substances that interact with proteins in the cell walls, providing increased strength and rigidity, thereby limiting the movement of the pathogen. This aligns with findings by Hibar *et al.* (2007), which highlighted the role of peroxidase in thickening cell walls through the oxidation of phenolic compounds. The oxidized phenolics are converted into substances like hydrogen peroxide and quinones, which release free radicals such as $-OH$ and O_2 . These radicals activate genes directly responsible for the polymerization of lignin compounds, as noted in previous studies (Lavania *et al.*, 2006). Lignin deposition strengthens and hardens cell walls, particularly in the sclerenchymatous regions of xylem vessels, especially in wounded areas. Additionally, peroxidase contributes defensively to plant responses against pathogens by polymerizing and depositing proteins, lignin,

and suberin in vascular cell walls. This process enhances cell resistance by restricting pathogen movement through the vessels and acting as an antioxidant against oxidative stress induced by pathogen invasion (Dicko *et al.*, 2006).

The Effect of Maize Husks Fermented with Mycorrhizal Fungi and the Interaction of the Pathogenic Fungi *F. oxysporum* and *R. solani* on the Total Sugar Content in Leaves (PPM)

The results indicate that maize husks fermented with the fungi *G. applanatum* and *G. resinaceum* had a clear impact on the average total sugar content in the leaves (Table 6). The highest average total sugar content in the leaves was observed in the treatment with corn cobs fermented with *G. resinaceum* (50%) + soil (50%), where the average total sugar content in the leaves was 7.89 ppm, significantly higher than the other treatments. This was followed by the treatment with corn cobs fermented with *G. applanatum* (50%) + soil (50%), which had an average total sugar content of 7.75 ppm. The lowest average total sugar content in the leaves

was found in the treatment with soil (75%) + corn cobs (25%), where the total phenol content was 3.24 ppm. As for the pathogenic fungi, the total sugar content in the leaves for *F. oxysporum* and *R. solani* was 4.97 ppm and 4.66 ppm, respectively.

In the interaction, the highest total sugar content was observed in the combination of corn cobs

fermented with *G. resinaceum* (50%) + soil (50%) and the control treatment, where the total sugar content was 8.97 ppm, surpassing all other treatments. The lowest total sugar content was found in the interaction between soil (75%) + corn cobs (25%) and the pathogenic fungus *R. solani*, where the total sugar content in the leaves was 1.47 ppm.

Table 6. Effect of Corn Cobs Fermented with Mycorrhizal Fungi and the Interaction of the Pathogenic Fungi *F. oxysporum* and *R. solani* on the Total Sugar Content in Leaves (PPM)

Treatment	Control	<i>R. solani</i>	<i>F. oxysporium</i>	Mean
Soil only	6.48	1.51	1.94	3.36
75% soil + 25% corn cobs	6.33	1.47	1.88	3.24
50% soil + 50% corn cobs	6.77	1.64	1.91	3.47
75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. applanatum</i>	7.32	6.73	6.88	6.95
50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. applanatum</i>	8.17	7.18	7.34	7.57
75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. resinaceum</i>	7.64	6.93	7.17	7.23
50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. resinaceum</i>	8.97	7.17	7.48	7.89
Average of pathogenic fungi	7.35	4.66	4.97	
LSD	Cobs=0.18	Fungi=0.11	Interaction=0.31	

The *Ganoderma* mushroom contains numerous bioactive compounds, including fibers, polysaccharides, and essential minerals. It also possesses various other compounds that exhibit therapeutic properties for a wide range of diseases, in addition to their antimicrobial effects (Liang *et al.*, 2018; Cör and Knez, 2022). Among these, the polysaccharides and triterpenoids isolated from *Ganoderma* are considered the most significant pharmacological compounds, alongside other bioactivities such as antibiotic properties (Bhat *et al.*, 2019).

Effect of Fermented Corn Cobs with Fleshy Fungi and the Interaction of the Pathogenic Fungi *F. oxysporum* and *R. solani* on Total Vitamin Content in Leaves (ppm)

Table 7 demonstrates the significant impact of corn cobs fermented with the fungi *G. applanatum* and *G. resinaceum* on the average total vitamin content in leaves. The results showed that the highest total vitamin content in leaves was observed in the treatment combining 50% *G. resinaceum*-fermented corn cobs with 50% soil, where the total vitamin content reached 5.8

ppm, significantly outperforming the other treatments. This was followed by the treatment of 50% *G. applanatum*-fermented corn cobs combined with 50% soil, which recorded a total vitamin content of 5.5 ppm in the leaves. In contrast, the lowest total vitamin content in leaves was recorded in the "soil only" treatment and the treatment with 75% soil + 25% corn cobs, both of which showed a vitamin content of 1.9 ppm. Regarding the pathogenic fungi, the total vitamin content in leaves was 3.2 ppm for *F. oxysporum* and 3.1 ppm for *R. solani*.

For the interactions, the highest total vitamin content was observed in the combination of 50% *G. resinaceum*-fermented maize cobs + 50% soil with the control treatment, where the total vitamin content reached 6.9 ppm, significantly surpassing all other treatments. In contrast, the lowest total vitamin content was recorded in the interaction between "soil only" and the pathogenic fungus *R. solani*, with the total vitamin content in leaves measuring only 0.8 ppm.

Table 7. Effect of Corn Cobs Fermented with Fleshy Fungi and the Interaction of the Pathogenic Fungi *F. oxysporum* and *R. solani* on Total Vitamin Content in Leaves (ppm)

Treatment	Control	<i>R. solani</i>	<i>F. oxysporum</i>	Mean
Soil only	3.9	0.8	0.9	1.9
75% soil + 25% corn cobs	4.1	0.9	0.9	1.9
50% soil + 50% corn cobs	4.1	0.9	0.9	2.1
75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. applanatum</i>	5.3	4.1	4.2	4.5
50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. applanatum</i>	6.5	4.9	5.1	5.5
75% soil + 25% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. resinaceum</i>	5.6	4.2	4.3	4.7
50% soil + 50% corn cobs fermented with <i>G. resinaceum</i>	6.9	5.2	5.4	5.8
Average of pathogenic fungi	5.2	3.1	3.2	
LSD	Cobs=0.26	Fungi=0.17	Interaction=0.45	

The use of biotic and abiotic elicitors leads to an increase in ascorbic acid levels in chloroplasts and other plant parts. Ascorbic acid is one of the important components in redox reactions in plant cells and is an important molecule in plant defense (Farmer and Mueller, 2013). This is in accordance with the results from Hassan et al. (2020) whether *T. viride* and *T. harzianum* biocontrol fungal treatment leads to ↑ proline and ascorbic acid content in *F. oxysporum* infected tomato plants. Furthermore, Ganoderma spp. extract and filtrate N. 2017 and Hassan and Awad (2017) showed that they are in the context of the availability of essential nutrients; strongly affect plant growth, including its physiological and biochemical processes, as well as qualitative traits (vitamins).

The results indicated significant differences among fungal isolates obtained from cucumber plants, demonstrating a substantial impact on reducing the germination rate of cucumber seeds used in the study. The fungus *F. oxysporum* showed a significant superiority over other fungal isolates, with a germination rate of 13.13%, except for the isolate of *R. solani*, which exhibited a germination rate of 16.13%. This was in contrast to the control treatment, where the germination rate reached 90%.

Conclusion

The field experiment results demonstrated that the treatment combining 50% soil with 50% maize cobs fermented by *G. resinaceum* with the interaction of the two pathogenic fungi resulted

in the highest total phenolic content in leaves, reaching 138.64 ppm. The treatment with 50% soil and 50% maize cobs fermented by *G. applanatum* recorded a total phenolic content of 137.47 ppm. Regarding total glycoside content under the interaction of the pathogenic fungi, the treatment of 50% soil + 50% maize cobs fermented by *G. resinaceum* outperformed others, with a total glycoside content of 57.65 ppm. The glycoside content of the treatment of 50% soil + 50% maize cobs fermented by *G. applanatum* was 56.91 ppm. The maximum peroxidase content of 20.23 ppm for *G. resinaceum* treatment along with the pathogenic fungi was 50% soil + 50% maize cobs fermented whereas highest peroxidase content was 50% soil + 50% maize cobs fermented by *G. resinaceum* treatment.

For total sugar, the highest content of total sugar was observed in a treatment of 50% soil + 50% maize cobs fermented by *G. resinaceum* in the interaction of the two pathogenic fungi, which was equal to 7.89 ppm, significantly more than other treatments, except for the treatment of 50% soil + 50% maize cobs fermented by *G. applanatum*, which had a total sugar content of 7.57 ppm.

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